

Effect of Dicofol Induced Alterations in the Protein Contents of the Fresh Water Bivalve, *Parreysia cylindrica*"

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Abstract:-

In present investigation the effect of toxicity results are expressed as LC₅₀ (lethal concentration) values. From LC₅₀ values safe concentration of a toxicant can be determined. This is useful for the study of physiological responses to the toxicant in organism of dicofol on total protein contents in different tissues i.e. mantle, foot, gills, digestive glands, gonads and whole soft body tissues after chronic exposure. The synthetic dicofol causes serious pollution problem in aquatic environment. The variation in protein contents in different tissues to dicofol of fresh water bivalve, *Parreysia cylindrica* was studied. The bivalves were exposed to (0.04023 ppm) as chronic treatment, decrease in total protein content of all tissues was observed with an increased exposure time. The most change of protein content occurs in digestive gland followed by gills, mantle, whole soft body and foot.

Key words : Dicofol , Protein content, *Parreysia cylindrica*.

Introduction:-

The Pesticide Survey, USA 1987 through 1996, reports that the total annual domestic agricultural usage of dicofol averaged about 860,000 ponds active ingredient for about 720,000 acres (2,900 km²) treated. Most of the area is treated with 2 pounds a.i. or less per application, and the average acre is treated with about 1.2 pounds a.i. per year (1.3 kg/ ha/yr). Fruits tend to have the highest application rates. The largest markets for dicofol in terms of total pounds active ingredient are cotton (over 50%) and citrus (almost 30%). Although only about 4% of the cotton acres grown are treated with dicofol, over 60% of all crop acres treated with dicofol are cotton acres. The remaining usage is primarily on other fruits and vegetables. Most of the US usage is in California and Florida. Krishnamurthy and David (2010) studied the impact of dicofol on toxicity and behavioral responses of the fresh water fish, *Labeo rohita*. Gopala Rao *et al.*, (2006) studied the toxicity and effects of dicofol on the fresh water fish, *Channa punctatus*.

Several reports are available on the toxicity of organochlorine pesticides to fish species and other related animals. Doudroff *et al.*, (1953) studied the toxicity of some organic insecticides to the fish. Carndall and Goodnight (1962) studied the effect of sub-lethal concentrations of several toxicants of most commercially importance and common guppy fish, *Lebistes reticulate*. Eisler (1970) studied latent effect of insecticides to the intoxicant to marine mollusc. Arora (1971) have studied the bioassay effect of some commercially organic insecticides on exotic carp, *Puntius sophore* (Ham.). Arora *et al.*, (1972) studied the bioassay effect of six organic insecticides on freshwater fish, *Cirrhinus mrigala* (Ham.). Toor *et al.*, (1973) studied the toxicity of an exotic fish from a common carp *Cyprinus carpio*. Reddy and Gomathy (1977) studied the toxicity and respiratory effect of pesticide thiodan on catfish *Mystus vittus*. Rao and Murty (1980) studied bio-

transformation and elimination of endosulfan on *Anabas testidineus*. Dalela (1980) and Dehadrai (1990) recorded significant metabolic stress from fishes. The investigation regarding the biochemical changes after pesticide exposure and its subsequent recovery in non target aquatic species such as molluscs was insufficient. Hence in the present study an attempt was made to investigate the effect of chronic treatment of pesticide dicofol and its subsequent recovery by exogenous administration of L-ascorbic acid on the protein contents of different soft body tissues of fresh water bivalve, *Parreysia cylindrica*. Synthetic organic pesticides are used to control weeds, insects and other organisms in a wide variety of agricultural and non-agricultural settings. any undesirable change in the environment affects the protein level by changing the physiology of organism. Various toxicants like heavy metals, pesticides etc are known to disturb the protein metabolism in the body of organism. Young (1970) suggested that, dynamic equilibrium mechanism in the internal environment of organism changes the protein content of cell periodically by the degradation and synthesis. In aquatic bodies, these pesticides affect many non target organisms due to biomagnifications through food chains. Pickering and Henderson (1966) reported the acute toxicity of some pesticides to fish which indicate that several of these pesticides are extremely toxic and could represent a hazard to aquatic life. Pesticides and other toxic chemical cause such harmful effect on varieties of aquatic animals like frog, fishes, crabs, mussels etc (Rajagopalan, 2005). A major environmental impact has been the widespread mortality of fish and marine invertebrates due to the contamination of aquatic systems by pesticides. Most of the fish in Europe's Rhine River were killed by the discharge of pesticides, and at one time fish populations in the Great Lakes became very low due to pesticide contamination. It is evident that pesticides cause major losses in global fish

production. Konar (1975) reported the mass mortality of commercial fishes due to washing Organochlorine insecticides by heavy rains in adjacent aquatic resources. According to Jhingran (1974), in India majority of fish population die due to water pollution and increased use of pesticides in agriculture. The poisoning by pesticides from agricultural fields is a serious water pollution problem and its environmental long term effect may result in the incidence of poisoning of fish and other aquatic life forms (Jyothi and Narayan, 1996). Owing to the excessive use of pesticides, the environment and water resource are being polluted, thus endangering aquatic life directly and human life indirectly (Gill *et al.*, 1988). Dicofol is an organochlorine (OC), widely used alone or in mixture as an insecticide. It is differ from most other OPS in that it produces an insecticidal concentration of a vapor that make it promising for the control of malaria transmission. dicofol is used to control household, public health, and stored product insects. It is effective against mushroom flies, aphids, spider mites, caterpillars, thrips, and white flies in greenhouse, outdoor fruit, and vegetable crops (Meister, 1992). Therapeutically, Organochlorine is available in aerosol and soluble concentrate formulations. It is used as a fumigant (Meister, 1992) and has been used to make pet collars and pest strips (Hayes and Laws, 1990). Organochlorine is a broad spectrum insecticides that provides rapid beat down with short residual effect, which makes it safe and effective insecticide. It is soluble in water and contains an active in gradient dicofol by about 18.5%. The present investigation was aimed to study biochemical changes in the different tissue of fresh water bivalve *Parryisia cylindrica* after sub-lethal exposure to dicofol.

Materials and Methods:-

For the experimental studies the animals were divided into three groups

1. **Group 'A'** was maintained as control.
2. **Group 'B'** animals were exposed to chronic concentration (LC 50/10 values of 96 hrs) of dicofol (0.04023 PPM) up to 21 days
3. **Group 'C'** animals were exposed to chronic concentration of dicofol (0.04023 ppm) along with 50 mg / l L-ascorbic acid up to 21 days.

Experimental design for recovery studies : Set- II

Group 'B' animals from set-I were divided into two groups for recovery study

D. Animals pretreated to Dicofol were allowed to self-cure naturally in untreated fresh water up to 21 days .

E. Animals pretreated to dicofol, were allowed to cure in 50mg / l L- ascorbic acid in fresh water up to 21 days.

During experimentation animals were fed on fresh water algae. After every 7th, 14th and 21st days of

interval animals from set-I and set-II were taken out, dissected and tissues such as digestive glands, gonad, gills, foot, mantle were separated and whole body mass of remaining animals was taken. All tissues were dried at 70 – 80^o C in an oven till constant weights were obtained. The dried powders of different tissues of control and experimental animals were used for the estimation of total protein components. The methods of estimation are as follows:

Protein estimation:-

Protein content of the tissues was estimated by Lowry's method (Lowry *et al.*, 1951). 10 mg of dry powder was homogenized small amount of 10% TCA and the homogenate was diluted to 10 ml by 10% TCA. Then it was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The protein precipitate at the bottom of centrifuged tubes was dissolved in 10ml 1.0 N NaOH solution. 0.1 ml of this solution of each powder was taken in three test tubes containing 4.0 ml. freshly prepared Lowry's 'C'. After adding 0.5 ml. Folin's – phenol reagent, the test tubes were incubated in dark at 37^oC for 30 minutes. The O. D. of blue colour developed was read at 530 nm. The blank was prepared in same way without dissolved protein precipitate. The protein content in different tissues was calculated referring to standard graph value and it was expressed in terms of mg protein/100 mg of dry tissue. The Bovine serum albumen was used as a standard.

Results and Discussion:-

Present investigation is concerned with changes in biochemical composition in different tissues of *Parreysia cylindrica* exposed to chronic dose of pesticide dicofol and its subsequent recovery after withdrawal of pesticide and its subsequent recovery by exogenous administration of L-ascorbic acid. In the present study obtained results demonstrated that, after chronic exposure to pesticides dicofol a marked depletion in the protein contents in the mantle, foot, gills, gonad, digestive glands and whole soft body tissues of the experimental freshwater bivalve *Parreysia cylindrica* was observed as compared to bivalves maintained as control. The percentage of decreased in protein content after chronic treatment of 7, 14 and 21 days with dicofol was 31.12, 41.72 and 48.65 in mantle, 24.65, 31.64 and 39.32 in foot, 44.92, 57.71 and 57.04 in gills, 49.01, 64.97 and 66.37 in digestive glands, 21.03, 32.46 and 47.66 in gonad and 29.06, 42.76 and 48.81 in whole soft body. The percentage of decreased in protein content after chronic treatment of 7, 14 and 21 days with dicofol was 31.12, 41.72 and 48.65 in mantle, 24.65, 31.64 and 39.32 in foot, 44.92, 57.71 and 57.04 in gills, 49.01, 64.97 and 66.37 in digestive glands, 21.03, 32.46 and 47.66 in gonad and 29.06, 42.76 and 48.81 in whole soft body.

Table -1- Impact of Dicofol On Total Protein Contain tissues of fresh water bivalve, *Parreysia cylindrica* after chronic exposure.

Sr. No.	Tissue	(A) Control			(B) Dicofol		
		7 day	14 day	21 day	7 day	14 day	21 day
1.	Mantle	41.91 ± 1.12	39.91 ± 1.16	38.47 ± 1.52	30.16* ± 1.56 (-31.12)	21.91* ± 3.04 (-41.72)	18.16** ± 2.17 (-48.65)
2.	Foot	63.48 ± 2.42	63.23 ± 1.26	62.91 ± 1.32	47.83** ± 2.80 (-24.65)	43.22** ± 2.71 (-31.64)	38.17** ± 2.50 (-39.32)
3.	Gills	54.16 ± 2.48	53.70 ± 1.65	53.20 ± 2.67	29.83** ± 2.06 (-44.92)	25.93** ± 3.86 (-51.71)	22.85*** ± 2.04 (-57.04)
4.	Digestive glands	50.74 ± 1.25	51.16 ± 2.68	50.86 ± 2.55	25.87* ± 3.01 (-49.01)	17.92** ± 2.98 (-64.97)	17.10*** ± 2.37 (-66.37)
5.	Gonad	48.58 ± 2.88	48.21 ± 1.62	47.12 ± 1.93	38.36* ± 2.14 (-21.03)	32.56** ± 1.31 (-32.46)	24.66** ± 1.20 (-47.66)
6.	Whole soft body	61.66 ± 3.04	61.12 ± 1.58	60.72 ± 1.90	43.74** ± 1.05 (-29.06)	34.98** ± 2.41 (-42.76)	31.08*** ± 2.62 (-48.81)

1. Values expressed as mg/100mg dry wt. of tissue
2. (+) or (-) indicate percent variation over control
3. ± indicate S.D. of three observation
4. Values are significant at * $P < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.05$
5. NS (Not significant).

The decrease in amount of protein content in different tissues after chronic exposure to pesticides indicate that, pesticides inhibits the synthesis of protein which ultimately results in increase in the free amino acid pool in the cell or due to enhancement of proteolysis to cope with the high energy demands under toxic stress (Vincent *et al.*, 1995; Waykar and Lomte, 2001). A marked fall in the protein level in all the tissues indicates a rapid initiation of breakdown of protein. To meet energy demands during toxic stress mobilization of protein might have taken place. The depletion of protein tissue was due to diversification of energy, to meet the impending energy demand under toxic stress (Vincent *et al.*, 1995) and to prevent fatigue due to pesticide toxicity (Parate and Kulkarni, 2003). At high pollution stress however, protein synthesis can be suppressed indicating disturbance of normal metabolic processes (Pottinger *et al.*, 2002). The results of total protein contents in all tissues clearly indicate that digestive glands was the most affected organ followed by gill, whole body, mantle, gonads and foot. The higher depletion of protein in the digestive gland might be due to high metabolic potency and efficiency of the gland when compared

to other tissues like mantle, foot, gills, gonads and whole soft body of the bivalve. The digestive gland is the site of action of pollutants in the body of bivalves or digestive gland seems to be the main site of degradation and detoxification of pesticides and hence has the largest demand of energy for the metabolic processes resulting into increasing utilization of protein in digestive gland provides better indication of the extent of toxicity. Mule and Lomte (1992, 1993, and 1995), Waykar and Lomte (2001) supported the most alteration of protein contents in digestive glands of freshwater bivalves. Patil (2011) observed maximum depletion of protein content in digestive glands than in mantle, gills, foot and whole body tissue. Depletion of protein content in animal tissue after exposure to various pollutants was reported by some workers. Ramana Rao and Ramamurthi (1978) observed alteration in protein content in tissue of *Pila globosa* after sumithion exposure. Lomte and Alam (1982) reported depletion of protein content in various body tissue of snails, after malation significant decline in protein content in fresh water mussel *Lamellidens marginalis* exposed to flodit and metacid. Similar observation were made by number of workers in molluse (Maneetal 1986), Muley and Mane 1989), Mule and Lomte 1993, 1995). Thus the result obtained in the present study indicate severe disturbances in the protein metabolisms of the bivalve, *Parreysia cylindrica* exposed to dicofol.

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